

AZINE DYES DERIVED FROM 3:4- AND 2:1-PHENANTHRA- THIOPHENE-2':3'-DIONES

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Azine dyes derived from 3:4- and 2:1-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-diones are described.

3:4- and 2:1-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-diones have been obtained by the interaction of oxalyl chloride with the corresponding 3-thiol-(Field, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1214) and 2-thiol-(Dutta and Chaudhury, *this issue*, p. 169) phenanthrenes respectively, followed by cyclisation with anhydrous aluminium chloride. The reasons for accepting the proposed structures of the diones have already been dealt with in another communication in this issue (*loc. cit.*). The diones have been condensed with *ortho*-diamines viz., *o*-phenylenediamine, 2:3-diaminoquinoxalin and 2:3-diaminophenazine to yield the corresponding azines, the colour of which deepens as usual with the increase in the number of azine rings in the molecule. The following table gives a comparison of the colour of these compounds and their dyeings on wool with those of the 9:10-isomers (Dutta and Sinha, *this Journal*, 1941, 18, 477). It is now found that the position of the additional 5-membered ring in the phenanthrene nucleus has very little effect on the colour of these azine dyes unlike the dyes of the thioindigoid series.

TABLE I
P stands for phenanthrathiophene.

Compound.	Colour of the compounds.	Colour of dyeings on wool.
9:10-P-phenazine	Sulphur-yellow	Yellow
3:4-P- "	Deep yellow	Pale yellow
2:1-P- "	Yellow	Light yellow
Quinoxaline-9:10-P-azine	Dull red	Orange
" 3:4-P- "	Deep red	Brown
" 2:1-P- "	Red	Orange-yellow
9:10-P-phenazinazine	Chocolate	Chocolate
3:4-P- "	Dark chocolate	Chocolate
2:1-P- "	Dark chocolate	Chocolate

E X P E R I M E N T A L

3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (I)

3-Thiophenanthrene (5 g.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (10 c.c.) and the mixture left overnight at room temperature. The excess of oxalyl chloride was then distilled off and the residue after the addition of carbon disulphide (20 c.c.) was treated slowly with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.) and refluxed for an hour when gradually a dark violet complex formed. The carbon disulphide was next distilled off, the residue treated with crushed ice and hydrochloric acid (conc.), filtered and washed. For purification, the residue was repeatedly extracted with warm dilute sodium carbonate solution (10%) and the product obtained as a red precipitate by acidifying the reddish yellow alkali solution with hydrochloric acid. Recrystallisation from a large volume of hot alcohol and then from glacial acetic acid yielded the pure product in fine red needles, m. p. 239-40°. (Found: C, 72.68; H, 3.17. $C_{18}H_{10}O_2S$ requires C, 72.72; H, 3.03 per cent).

3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-phenazine (II)

o-Phenylenediamine (0.8 g.) was added to a solution of 3:4-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.2 g.) in acetic acid (15 c.c.) and on shaking the colour of the solution immediately became lighter with the separation of fine yellow needles. The reaction mixture was boiled for 15 minutes, filtered hot and the crystals washed with acetic acid and finally with alcohol. It was crystallised from pyridine in golden yellow needles, m. p. 287°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a beautiful violet colour. (Found: C, 78.48; H, 3.69. $C_{22}H_{13}N_2S$ requires C, 78.57; H, 3.57 per cent).

Quinoxaline-3:4-phenanthrathiophenazine (III) was prepared from 3:4-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.3 g.) and 2:3-diaminoquinoxaline (0.15 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) as described above. It was crystallised from pyridine in beautiful felted red needles, m. p. above 290°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a greenish blue colour. (Found: N, 14.13. $C_{24}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

3:4-Phenanthrathiophene-phenazinazine (V) was prepared as stated above from 3:4-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.3 g.) and 2:3-diaminophenazine (0.2 g.). It was purified by dissolving it in the minimum quantity of hot pyridine and diluting with water just to turbidity; on standing gradually chocolate crystalline mass separated out, m. p. above 290°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour. (Found: N, 12.58. $C_{20}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 12.78 per cent).

2:1-Phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (V)

2-Thiophenanthrene (2 g.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (4 c.c.) and on slight warming gradually the thiol compound dissolved with a yellow solution which after a short time solidified to a red crystalline mass. After allowing it to stand for 24 hours the excess of oxalyl chloride was distilled off, carbon disulphide (20 c.c.) added and treated with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.4 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for an hour until the evolution of hydrochloric acid ceased; the carbon disulphide was next distilled off and the residue decomposed with a mixture of crushed ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product after filtration was extracted with benzene, the red benzene extract concentrated when a red crystalline mass, contaminated with a yellow substance, was obtained. For purification, it was extracted with warm sodium carbonate solution (10%) and the extract on acidification with hydrochloric acid precipitated the dione as a red mass which on two-crystallisations from a large volume of hot alcohol yielded the pure product as red needles, sintering at 226°, m. p. 232°. (Found: C, 72.65; H, 3.13. $C_{11}H_8O_2S$ requires C, 72.72; H, 3.03 per cent).

2:1-Phenanthrathiophene-phenazine (VI)

o-Phenylenediamine (0.75 g.) and 2:1-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.25 g.) were dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) when the colour of the solution immediately became lighter and yellow needles separated out. The reaction mixture on being refluxed for 15 minutes was filtered, the crystals washed with glacial acetic acid, followed by alcohol and recrystallised from pyridine in golden yellow glistening needles, m. p. 274°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour. (Found: N, 8.27. $C_{22}H_{12}N_2S$ requires N, 8.33 per cent).

Quinoxaline-2:1-phenanthrathiophenazine (VII) was prepared as above from 2:1-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.3 g.) and 2:3-diaminoquinoxaline (0.15 g.). Recrystallisation from benzene gave the product in beautiful red silky needles, m. p. 230°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet colour. (Found: N, 14.39. $C_{24}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

2:1-Phenanthrathiophene-phenazinazine (VIII)

It was prepared from 2:1-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.3 g.) and 2:3-diaminophenazine (0.25 g.) as described above. For purification, it was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot pyridine and diluted with water just to turbidity; on standing gradually a dark chocolate crystalline mass separated out, m.p. above 290°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a blackish violet colour. (Found: N, 12.69, $C_{28}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 12.78 per cent).

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